

Fig. 1: [higher is better] Average speedup across all the codes from the 10 validation folds when using different combinations of flag-sequences. **training exploration** refers to the flag selection method originally used in the paper (step E in figure 1 of the paper). After training the static model to predicts configurations, we use it over the training folds to evaluate its prediction across all the flag-sequences. We keep the flag-sequence that performs the best. **single overall flag seq** refers to the single flag-sequence that provides that best overall gains across all the codes (to be used in all cases). **oracle flag per code** refers to the gains that are achieved if we select the best possible flag-sequence for each code individually. In the paper, this flag-sequence is called *Best Flag*. This is the oracle gains that can be achieved if we are able to select for every code the most efficient flag-sequence. Finally, **prediction flag seq** (in red) refers to a new model that predicts flag-sequences as suggested by the review. We describe this model in the supplements.

Fig. 2: [higher is better] Speedup of the compilation time over the execution time for different codes. Only CG CLASS A was faster to compile than to execute. The fast compilation highlights the gains of the static approaches over dynamic ones.

Performance difference when optimizing size-2 with size-1 configurations

Fig. 3: [lower is better] Slowdown per code over size-2 inputs measured for each code as:

$$Slowdown_{code} = 1 - Execution\ Time_{using\ the\ best\ configuration\ for\ size\ 2}^{on\ size\ 2} / Time_{using\ the\ best\ configuration\ for\ size\ 1}^{on\ size\ 1}$$

Over these regions, if we perform a full configuration exploration over size-1 (more than 300 points), and then apply the found configurations per code over size-2, we observe an average 3.2% losses compared to a full exploration natively done over size-2. Size-1 refers to CLASS A and largest inputs for NAS and Rodinia respectively while size-2 refers to CLASS B and smaller inputs. Executing size-2 codes with size-1 configurations provides an average $1.6\times$ speedup.

Fig. 4: Execution time per call (in cycles) of the 4 miss-predicted regions along SP as reference for a stable behavior across calls. Regions that we failed to predict have different execution times per call resulting in different behaviors at runtime.

Number of predictions across labels

Fig. 5: Number of predictions per label for SkyLake natively trained using 6 labels. **Oracle** refers to the number of times a label is marked for a code. **Predicted** presents the number of times our model predicted the label. **Correct** shows how many of these predictions were correct. We gather all the codes from the 10 validation folds to estimate the predictions per label.

REBUTTAL SUPPLEMENT

Because of space constraints, we did not include these points in our rebuttal. We fully understand if they are not considered.

- Due to system constraints, all the executions of the rebuttal were performed on a new SkyLake (Xeon Gold 6130) using Clang 6. We executed the full applications for all the plots except Rebuttal-fig. 3 for which we relied on sampled execution as described in [12] due to the huge search space.
- Rebuttal-fig. 2 compares compilation time (serial -O3) with execution time over different codes. We observe that for small applications, the compilation time is similar to the execution time. However, as expected larger applications take an order of magnitude longer to execute than to compile.
- To train and evaluate our new flag-sequence model, we investigated the most efficient overall flag-sequences and gathered them into lists to use as labels. 2 and 4 sequences were necessary on SkyLake and SandyBridge respectively to reach 99% of oracle flag gains. Then, using the current static model workflow, we generated a vector for each code and used it as features (that we explore with GA) along with the flag-sequence labels to train a new classification tree to select the flag-sequence to use to statically predict a configuration. Finally, we validated the new model with the 10 folds procedure.
- To the best of our knowledge, only reaction based performance counters [12] have been successful at optimizing the coupled search space of NUMA and prefetchers. We will further explore other static approaches in future work.
- ProGraML [32] represents IR as graphs that are used to optimize mapping for heterogeneous devices. We only reuse their graph representation.
- We assume that applications run alone on the system. Co-executing applications will change the best configurations due to contention over shared resources: we would need to explore new labels with the co-executed applications.
- As mentioned by the review, some variables dominate the performance and are marked as labels more often. Rebuttal-fig. 5 presents the predictions per label for SkyLake with 6 labels natively trained. Because some labels have very little instances (e.g. label 6 occurs 2 times), they are difficult to correctly predict. Adding more codes could alleviate this issue. Nevertheless, it seems that the miss-predictions are mostly correlated with the oracle numbers indicating that there are no major label that our model systematically misses. We will address our paper to be more representative of these observations.
- The full space of NUMA configurations include: thread mapping (scatter or contiguous), data mapping (locality, interleave, balance, first touch, single node), degree of parallelism, and NUMA degree [12,34]. The prefetcher includes the full exploration of the following 4 prefetchers: DCU IP-correlated prefetcher, DCU prefetcher, L2 adjacent cache line prefetcher, and the L2 streamer prefetcher [33].